

Report on the third NFDI Berlin-Brandenburg network meeting: Artificial intelligence as an enabler for science

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On May, 21, the NFDI consortium for Data Science and Artificial Intelligence (NFDI4DS) and the mathematical NFDI consortium (MaRDI) jointly held the third meeting of the NFDI Berlin-Brandenburg (NFDI_BB) community, thus continuing a series of meetings kicked off in 2023. Since Artificial Intelligence (AI) was identified as a central task overarching most of the consortia during the previous NFDI_BB network meeting in July 2024, the topic of the present meeting was chosen to be ‘**AI as an enabler for science**’.

The one-day workshop took place from 09:00 a.m. to 4:00 p.m. at the Weizenbaum Institute for the Networked Society (German Internet Institute) in Berlin-Charlottenburg. Around 40 participants from ca 16 NFDI consortia joined the meeting. The two keynote speeches, complemented by seven contributions from individual consortia, essentially covered two topics, namely AI methods with data and Knowledge Graphs (KGs).

Figure 1: Participants of the third NFDI_BB meeting

within the FAIRMat consortium. In particular he presented the solid state physics database NOMAD, a federated ecosystem, including electronic lab notebooks, for novel materials discovery.

- **Christoph Scheurer** from the Fritz Haber-Institute reported on recent progress in self-driving Lab (SDL) approaches based on AI methods within the NFDI4Cat consortium. Despite of the high degree of automatization of workflows, the speaker still emphasized the role of the “human in the loop”.
- **Tilman Hickel** from the *Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung* explored automated workflows and machine learning for multi-scale materials science simulations within the MatWerk consortium and provided a practical introduction to workflow management using the Pyiron toolbox.

Afternoon Session

The session began with the interesting keynote speech by **Georg Rehm** from the German Research Center for Artificial Intelligence (DFKI), working in the field of computational linguistics. In particular, he reported on so called “shared tasks”, which provide a framework for scientifically exciting and challenging tasks for the data science and artificial intelligence community. A shared task is a community-driven scientific competition to solve a specific problem. One example of a shared task was shown to be a research field classification.

Subsequently, four interesting tool demos showcasing the use of artificial intelligence in the individual consortia.

- **Tim Conrad** from the Zuse Institute Berlin talked about transitioning from queries to conversations for expanding the access to the KG of the MaRDI consortium. In particular, the speaker showed a prototype of a chatbot interacting with the MaRDI KG which is part of the MaRDI portal.
- **Marcus Schmidt** from *Leibniz-Zentrum für Agrarlandschaftsforschung* (ZALF) discussed about where and how AI could be used to improve the quality of the FAIRagro consortium helpdesk to support the Research Data Management (RDM) of the community. The aim is to understand their customer needs, find relevant resources, datasets and tools, etc.
- **Daniel Mietchen** from Leibniz-Institut für Informationsinfrastruktur (FIZ) and Wikidata, working within MaRDI and KGI4NFDI, presented Scholia, a Python package and webapp for scholarly information based on Wikidata, also offering curation tools.
- **Sonja Schimmler** from FOKUS and Technical University Berlin gave an overview of services within the NFDI4DS consortium, specifically focusing on their Gateway and Portal. The service is meant to give access to digital research artifacts from the data science and artificial intelligence domain.

Final Discussion

In summary, the workshop highlighted two areas of the use of AI systems in the research process:

- AI as a tool in the scientific workflow covering efficient data acquisition, data analysis, multi-scale modeling (e.g. to speed up simulations), design of experiments (both in the lab and in modeling), and data-informed science (e.g. identification of mathematical models from data).
- AI and Chatbots based on LLMs, RAG or other approaches as a gateway to databases, scientific knowledge and scholarly publications.

Both approaches are being actively developed and/or pursued throughout many NFDI consortia. FAIR research data and knowledge graphs are always a prerequisite for an efficient prototyping and sustainable development of such systems.

To conclude the workshop, another Mentimeter session moderated by Christine Hennig, to obtain additional feedback from the attendees. The questions covered:

- How did you like the event?
- How did you like the demo sessions?
- Which tools would you show (or watch) in 10 or 20 years?
- Which ideas did you get for your work?
- Which topics could you imagine for the next NFDI_BB meeting?

Figure 3: Wordcloud: topics for future NFDI_BB network meetings

Outlook

Upon a final discussion with the participants, suggested topics for future meetings among others were: training and education, transparency, reproducibility and

fairness; while interactive formats like open space have been suggested.

Contact

For feedback on this report, and for suggesting future meeting topics, please send us an email: nfdi_bb@mardi4nfdi.de

Note that the NFDI_BB mailing list will continue to be the main communication channel for information on future NFDI_BB activities:

https://www.listserv.dfn.de/sympa/info/nfdi_bb

The presentations held at the meeting as well as the complete Mentimeter surveys are available at the NFDI_BB community at Zenodo,